

ELDERS LEARNING ENGLISH FOR EUROPE

THE PORTUGUESE CASE

This study investigates motivational factors and language learning strategies involved in the process of learning English as a Foreign Language (EFL) in the elderly. This needs' analysis report is part of the implementation of ERASMUS+ project nr 2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465.

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ELDERS LEARNING ENGLISH FOR EUROPE

The Portuguese Case

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INTRODUCTION

Europe is aging dramatically; in 30 years, the Portuguese will be the oldest. Sub-Saharan Africa will be the world's demographic motor in the 21st century, and India will be ahead of China in 2024 in terms of population, according to a report by the EP think-tank. The European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS) looked at the demographic outlook for the European Union, pointing out that, according to Eurostat's baseline forecast, the EU-28 population will reach 528.6 million in 2050 and start to decline thereafter.¹

Demographic change in the European Union (EU) is likely to have a significant impact in the coming decades as models looking at future demographic trends show that persistently low fertility rates will continue to age the EU population as people increase their lives. While migration plays an important role in the demographic dynamics of European countries, migration alone will almost certainly not reverse the continuing trend that many EU regions are experiencing, namely the aging of the population. The social and economic impact of an aging population is likely to have serious repercussions across Europe, both at national and regional levels. For example, low fertility rates will reduce the number of students in the education sector, there will be fewer working-age people to support the rest of the population, and a higher proportion of older people (some of which will require additional infrastructure, health services and adapted apartments). These structural demographic changes can affect governments' ability to increase tax revenues, balance their finances, and provide sufficient pensions and healthcare services.² Older people accounted for a particularly high proportion of the total population in the rural and remote regions of Greece, Spain, France and Portugal, as well as regions in eastern Germany.

As a result, by 2050, there will be only two people of working age (15-64) in the EU for every person aged 65 or over, which, according to EPRS, is a "dramatic change" from the situation in 2001, when this relation was one to four.³

In 2021 the population of Portugal was 10,143,000. The average age increased from 31.0 in 1960 to 45.3. Urban population has increased from 5,597,602 (54.4%) in 2000 to 6,783,000 (67.1%) in the current year.

The population growth rate is minus 0.33% (35,000 residents, including 112,497 deaths). The demographics of Portugal constitutes of 5,316,000 women and 4,793,000 men, which means there are 902 men per 1000 women. Age distribution of the population: 17.6% of the population (1,776,327) under the age of 20, 59.0% of the population (5,960,856) between the age of twenty and sixty-four, and 23.5% of the population (2,372,817) over sixty five years⁴.

¹ <https://forsal.pl/artykuly/1423440,europa-starzeje-sie-dramatyczny-najgorzej-jest-w-portugalii.html>

² https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Archive:Statystyka_dotycz%C4%85ce_ludno%C5%9Bci_na_poziomie_regionalnym&oldid=204791

³ <https://forsal.pl/artykuly/1423440,europa-starzeje-sie-dramatyczny-najgorzej-jest-w-portugalii.html>

The population of Portugal over 65 is third in Europe, behind Italy and Greece. The European average is 20.1%; Portugal has 21.7% of the population over the age of 65. The phenomenon of aging is a global problem.

When analyzing the longevity of citizens, Portugal again ranks third in Europe, behind Italy and Greece, with 157 elderly people per 100 young people.

In the biggest tourist areas, one can almost always find someone who speaks major European languages. The hotel staff needs to speak a little English. French has almost disappeared as a second language.

German-speaking people are rare. About 32% of Portuguese can speak and understand English and 24% can understand and speak French. Despite the fact that Spanish is well understood, only 9% of people can speak it quickly.

Helping a foreigner is considered a pleasant and beneficial thing. If you try to speak Portuguese correctly, and especially go beyond clichéd phrases, you will be treated with respect. And the locals will apologize for the "difficulty" you learn Portuguese and encourage you in any way possible. This can encourage travelers to learn the basics of the Portuguese language, such as a daily greeting or the usual "thank you please".⁵

LONG LIFE LEARNING EDUCATION

According to our research, there are 153 seniors per 100 young people in Portugal. Portugal has many initiatives to combat the social exclusion of seniors, and a Senior University has also been established. Portugal is the 3rd oldest country in the European Union in terms of the number of seniors. It is also influenced by the departure of young Portuguese people to countries such as England and Ireland.

Older people often suffer from social exclusion, loneliness and depression. There are many posters in Portugal that address the problem and try to highlight the seriousness of the situation. There are projects that try to introduce a more active life including education and increasing the visibility of older people among younger people.

The project of the senior university was created with the intention of improving the quality of life of the elderly. Classes try to stimulate learning, creativity and communication among the elderly.

RUTIS is a network of activities promoted by these universities, including cultural, social and educational activities. This network was officially established in November 2005. Most of them are private initiatives.

⁴ <https://www.populationof.net/pl/portugal/>

⁵ <https://poradnuk.com.ua/pl/j%C4%99zyki-urz%C4%99dowe-portugalii.htm>

There is no data on the percentage or number of Portuguese seniors learning English, but there are some learning opportunities. Most of them are not dedicated to seniors but to all people and they are usually not free.

RUTIS provides its services to seniors at prices ranging from 0 to around 15 euros per month. There are 45,000 students aged 50+, 300 subjects and 5,500 volunteer teachers. At RUTIS, people can learn in many aspects, including English.

Elderly people during the coronavirus pandemic also used public networks such as television to learn English. They used educational programs broadcasting for children teaching basic words and sentences in English. It was quite a popular form of learning by seniors during the COVID-19 epidemic.

FINDINGS

Thirty-four respondents from Portugal took part in the survey. The age of the respondents was focused mainly on mature people; 14.7% under 45, 8.8% between 45 and 50 years of age, 17.6% between 51 and 60; 35.3% between 61 and 70 and 23.5% 71 and over. A detailed list is presented in the diagram below.

What is your age?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

Most of the respondents were women - almost 60%.

What is your gender?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

Of all the respondents, 94% were Portuguese, and only 6% were Spanish. The summary is presented in the diagram below.

Where do you live?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

When the professional status is analyzed, it can be assumed that half of the respondents are retired, almost 30% of the respondents are working, 3 respondents run a household. While 3 respondents are unable to work, only one is unemployed and looking for work. The responses are presented in the chart below.

Are you currently...?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

When the place of residence was analyzed, 56% of the respondents were found to live in cities with more than 10,000 inhabitants. Cities with up to 100,000 inhabitants were in second place. The responses are presented in the chart below.

Size of the place of residence

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

The first area of research asked respondents what type of tourism they preferred. Cultural tourism and health tourism are of the greatest interest. Beach and adventure tourism was in second place; ecotourism was the least popular among seniors. A detailed list is presented in the chart below.

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

The respondents of this survey are often accompanied by family and friends. They reportedly do not travel alone or with people they met via the Internet. Thirty respondents out of 37 reported that they hardly ever travel with people they met via the Internet or met locally; only 1 senior replied that he liked this form of traveling while others abstained. The percentage set of answers is presented in the chart below.

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

The survey also aimed to analyze the barriers to which seniors are exposed when traveling. While 14 respondents reported a problem with the lack of financial resources, only 6 people indicated that they had never had problems with financial resources for trips. Difficulties related to not knowing a foreign language were defined as the last barrier. While 14 respondents indicated that they encountered this difficulty often or always during trips abroad, 15 respondents either did not have this problem or it was relatively rare. It can be assumed that communication problems may depend on the country to which they are going. For instance, residents make every effort to understand the arriving tourists in tourist destinations. It is worth adding that the Portuguese language is close to the Spanish language and this makes it much easier for Portuguese seniors to travel and communicate. The barrier related to the lack of time turned out

to be almost imperceptible; most answers were divided between rarely and sometimes, often was chosen by 8 respondents. A detailed list of the answers is presented in the chart below.

Qual das seguintes situações o/a impede de viajar?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

Based on the previous question, it is important to analyze the difficulties that affect learning a foreign language declared by seniors participating in the study in more detail.

The first concern is the fear of memorizing words - 20 respondents indicated that they agreed (13) or completely agreed (7) with this statement. Fear of speaking was in the second place - 19 respondents, and fear of making mistakes was ranked third (15 respondents). Besides, 15 respondents stated that they were generally reluctant to learn a foreign language. It is comforting that for each of the statements about the barriers related to learning a foreign language, a group of about 10 respondents did not agree with any of the statements. A detailed list of the answers is presented in the chart below.

Difficulty in learning a foreign language is:

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

The choice of a tool for learning a foreign language was another item indicated by the respondents. It was surprising that 17 respondents declared the use of paper books as the main tool supporting learning a foreign language; sometimes option would be chosen by 7 respondents; with rarely or never by 10 people. The rest of the responses matched the trend set because respondents were not interested in choosing e-books or board games. While 10 respondents indicated that they did not use board games before, 12 respondents that if they would use it, they would rarely do. Only 3 people chose to use board games to learn a foreign language. The task of the respondents on the use of a laptop to learn foreign languages was fairly evenly distributed: while 12 respondents indicated that they would sometimes use a computer for learning, 13 people indicated that would use it rarely or never; and only 9 respondents chose often and always.

It can be concluded after this stage of research that Portuguese seniors choose the methods of learning they know more willingly and do not like modern solutions of technological novelties. A detailed list of answers is available on the list below.

To learn a foreign language would you use

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

Another issue asked by researchers was the possibility of choosing the way of learning a foreign language during the COVID-19 pandemic. While 7 respondents indicated that they would certainly benefit from learning a foreign language via the website, 12 people responded it as probably. The e-learning platform was presented as the second option where 16 respondents indicated that they would definitely use it; 3 people said it was a very good idea. The e-learning platform is unlikely to be used by 10 people and certainly not by 5 people. The third way to learn a foreign language would be to use the application on the phone. Here 6 seniors would definitely and probably choose this option - 12 seniors; 12 respondents also indicated that it was possible. Only 4 respondents said they would not use this option. 18 respondents would choose watching movies in a foreign language as a language learning tool during the COVID-19 pandemic. This possibility does not exclude 10 seniors; 6 people firmly stated that they would not make such an attempt. As for the possibility of learning via DVDs or CDs, 22 respondents were not interested, and 12 people did not exclude such a possibility. Written materials such as textbooks were presented as the last tool; here 20 respondents claim that such a possibility is acceptable, there were 14 seniors who looked for such a solution. A detailed list can be found on the list below.

Eighteen respondents would choose watching movies in a foreign language as a language learning tool during the COVID-19 pandemic; this possibility does not exclude 10 seniors; 6 people firmly stated that they would not make such an attempt.

Looking at the possibility of learning via DVDs or CDs - 22 respondents are rather not interested, and 12 people do not exclude such a possibility. Written material was presented as the last tool; such as textbooks, here 20 respondents claim that such a possibility is acceptable, there were 14 seniors for such a solution. A detailed list can be found on the list below. Looking at the possibility of learning via DVDs or CDs - 22 respondents are rather not interested, and 12 people do not exclude such a possibility. Written material was presented as the last tool; such as textbooks, here 20 respondents claim that such a possibility is acceptable, there were 14 seniors for such a solution. A detailed list can be found on the list below.

Because of COVID-19 - If you could choose, which way would be the best for you to learn a language?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

Of all the respondents, 73.5% declared their willingness to learn English, yet 9 respondents (26.5%) did not express such willingness.

Have you ever travelled to a foreign country?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

Respondents were asked if they were interested in learning English in order to make better travels. While 58.8% of respondents declared their willingness to learn English, 41.2% did not express such willingness.

Would you be interested to learn English?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

Then, the respondents were asked about their motivation to learn English. The most frequent interest in learning the language was indicated by 22 respondents as follows: interest in culture (21 respondents), interest in contacts with people of the same age (20 responses); and interest in going shopping (16 respondents). Details are shown in the chart below.

Why would you study English?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

According to the respondents, mobile travel applications are used by them mainly to locate local attractions and eateries; yes and often: 17 respondents, not and rarely: 13 respondents; discovering new places: 15 respondents, and finding opinions about a place they want to visit: 17 respondents. As for getting detailed information about the destination, Always and often: 14 respondents ; Sometimes: 11 respondents, never or rarely: 9 respondents.

The possibility of booking hotels online was analyzed; 13 respondents used the dedicated applications always or often; 8 respondents used it sometimes; and 13 respondents used it never or rarely. While 9 respondents often or always used the option to purchase tickets online;

12 did this sometimes, and 13 do not do it online or very rarely. Portuguese seniors do not share travel photos or they do so rarely - 17 respondents: sometimes – 8: always and often - 11 respondents. Twenty respondents are unfamiliar with adding comments about the destination and sharing their opinion online, 10 do it rarely and only 4 people declared sharing their opinion on a regular basis.

A detailed list is presented in the chart below.

Use of travel apps as:

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

When asked about what should be included in future learning materials to improve their English, respondents indicated the followings respectively: Tips and tricks for independent learning (31 respondents); availability of modular sections for free download in pdf format (17 respondents); availability of free video downloads (24 respondents); links to social networks for communication (22 respondents); availability of the learning program for mobile devices and tablets (24 respondents). It is surprising that in the previous questions the respondents were not interested in learning with the use of tablets or computers - and here so many chose these possibilities.

A detailed list is presented in the diagram below.

What should be included in the prospective learning material to improve your English?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

When asked what they thought was missing from electronic materials used for learning English, the respondents most often indicated: ease of use(18 respondents);relevant illustrations (24 respondents);adequate

number of communication exercises (17 respondents);relevant content (20 respondents);connecting to internet sources(14 respondents);can be used on mobile devices(16 respondents).Detailed answers are presented in the diagrams below.

What do you think is lacking in the electronic materials used for English language learning?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

When respondents were asked about the desire to have their own application tailored to their individual needs which would help them in their travels, their answers were as follows: 7 respondents fully agreed; 13 seniors agreed; 7 respondents remained undecided, they disagreed with the statement of 5 respondents; and 2 respondents completely disagreed. Detailed answers are presented in the chart below.

Would you like to have your own application adapted to your needs to help you in your trips?

Source: Survey conducted in the Portuguese sample

CONCLUSION

Any additional comments to help us prepare a learning program useful for your needs?

Some responses are:

I don't travel because of a health problem that I can hardly walk. When I walk I am always limping. I already had cancer and I managed to recover but I have multiple sclerosis. 17 years ago the doctor said I had 12 years to stop walking but still I can barely but I can. So I never went anywhere else, and also because I don't know how to speak other languages

For those who want to learn a foreign language (in this case English), there is a lack of a program that teaches the beginning student. In the main bases of the language and not to speak like a wave for "mentally handicapped" that before they hear a single word of Language have to listen to the Life and Academic History of those who are teaching E-learning. A lot of time is wasted in telling Life Stories, Academics of other Students' processes and Less in putting Teaching into practice, starting with "A, B, C," ... as the Natives learned to speak.

Usually, when I try to learn English or install an application, they never meet my needs because either I start learning from 0 (which is the most common to find) or it's at a level ahead of mine and I don't understand anything about it.

When I was younger, I travelled a lot but now I'm getting older. I have a lot of health problems but I really enjoyed learning other languages and continuing to travel around the world. I also talk to a lot of foreign people but I use the translator to understand and be able to speak.

I already say a few things and I've travelled a lot and I've managed to get by. But sometimes it's even funny because I forget the words and people don't understand me and I keep trying to guess the word I'm missing ha-ha.

I always wanted to speak English and travel to other countries, but we don't always have enough money and also with the lack of my husband and I we have to not know how to speak English also makes it impossible for us to go, but it's more for the money

I don't know how to speak other languages other than Portuguese, a bad Spanish and a terrible one. However, I've travelled and I've managed to get by because either I go with people who understand and know how to speak English. I use a translator.

I think that basically a knowledge of the Portuguese language is necessary for a good learning of the idiom.

I don't know much about technologies but my children help me to try to understand, I think they are useful because you can do everything and research everything. It must be great to be able

to learn a foreign language. When I was younger, I could have only books because it was the only thing we had. However with this advance and these new technologies and also with my children they taught me. I am already better.

I don't know anything about technology, I'm not old enough for that, my wife and I are old and we don't even feel like traveling anymore. It's our children who are always bothering us to travel, so we're not always at home, and that's good .

I wasn't born in Portugal. I was born in Mozambique and my parents were Chinese. So the only languages I can speak are Chinese and Portuguese, and then I came to Portugal. I don't intend to go out again for money reasons.

There are many applications to learn a foreign language, but many of them are just for learning to speak correctly. However, I can't learn anything because I don't remember the meaning of words and also many applications are paid for several languages. I tried a few applications, but the only thing I was asked to do was read. Then they told me the meaning, and I can't learn that way.

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